

Table 1. Recovery of C and N.^a JAAS, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China.

Treatment	In raw materials		In compost				
	OM (kg)	N (kg)	C:N	OM (kg)	Recovery	N (kg)	Recovery
Local manure	195	2.93	23.4	80	0.41	1.88	0.64
Superphosphate	190	2.78	28.3	108	0.57	2.10	0.76

^a OM = organic matter.

Basic problems in using compost follow:

- 1) Unavoidable nutrition losses due to aeration process. Carbon losses ranged from 43 to 59%, N losses 24-36% (Table 2). The addition of superphosphate tended to reduce losses somewhat.

- 2) Labor to collect raw materials, prepare compost, transfer compost to field, and broadcast at 15 t/ha was estimated as 75 labor d/ha.
- 3) To guard against negative effect on rice seedlings, N fertilizer must be applied at 30 kg N to 10 t compost/ha. □

Table 2. Effect of rice straw compost on yield of double-cropped rice.^a

Treatment	1st crop		2d crop	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%)
Local manure	5.8	—	4.0	—
Compost 1	5.9	2.8	4.8	19.9
Compost 2	6.0	3.5	4.5	10.9

^a Local conventional manure = basal, N 0.153%, 45 t/ha (68.85 kg N); P₂O₅ 0.148%. Compost 1 = basal, N 0.302%, 15 t/ha (45.3 kg N); P₂O₅ 0.138%. Compost 2 = basal, N 0.285%, 15 t/ha (42.75 kg N); P₂O₅ 0.131%. In 1st crop, basal fertilizer for all treatments = 63.75 kg N/ha, topdressed fertilizer = 86.63 kg N/ha. In 2d crop, basal fertilizer for all treatments = 91.88 kg N/ha. Soil characteristics: irrigated lowland, clay loam, pH 6.8, 3.13% OM, 0.17% N, 0.156% P₂O₅, 17.4 ppm Olsen-P, 93.1 ppm NH₄Ac-K, CEC 20.3 meq/100 g.

Disease management

Effectiveness of five fungicides on rice sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn has become a problem in modern high-yielding varieties in Iran. We tested five fungicides for disease control (see table).

IR28 (Amol 2) was transplanted 2 May at 18 × 22 rows in 4- × 6-m plots. Herbicide was applied at 6 liters/ha 6 d after transplanting. Fertilizer was applied at 200 kg urea, 100 kg ammonium phosphate/ha 12 May simultaneously with transplanting, and 100 kg urea/ha was applied 19 Jul. All fungicides but IBP were applied with the sprayer delivering 1,000 liters/ha, IBP was broadcast by hand. Treatments were replicated five times in a randomized complete block design.

Fungicide applications were at booting and 10 d later, at heading. Degree of damage (DD) and degree of severity (DS%) were rated at harvest 17 Sep, and 80 hills/plot were harvested the

Effectiveness of fungicides on rice ShB. Bandar-Angali, Iran.

Treatment	Rate/ha	DD	DS (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Control		14.9	37	6.6
Iprodione ts 52.5PW	525 g	8	9.7	7.3
Validamycin 3% liquid	60 ml	3	7.2	7.4
Mepronil 50PW	500 g	6.8	1.1	6.9
Benomyl 50PW	500 g	5.2	12.7	6.3
IBP 17G	6800 g	2.5	6.1	7.6

day after. Grain was dried at room temperature and weighed. IBP, mepronil, validamycin, and

iprodione effectively controlled ShB. Yields were higher with IBP, validamycin, and iprodione. □

Cross-season perpetuation of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in Haryana, India

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We studied the perpetuation of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* Dye in infected leaves and artificially inoculated grains. Naturally infected leaves of variety Jaya were collected during the 1987 wet season, chopped into small pieces, and soaked in water for 30 min. The bacterial suspension was separated and injected in rice variety Jaya at 1 ml/boot. Grain was collected separately from inoculated boots and infected leaves, dried in the shade, and

kept at room temperature in the laboratory.

In 1988 wet season, inoculated grains were germinated on blotter paper, in pots, and in the field. Seedlings were tested for bacterial ooze at 1 wk (from blotter paper) and 10 d (from pots and field).

Seedlings grown in pots and transplanted in the field did not produce any symptoms of kresak and leaf blight.

A bacterial suspension prepared from stored infected leaves was used to inoculate TN1, Jaya, and Basmati 370 at maximum tillering in Aug 1988. Disease developed in all three varieties.

These tests show that *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* perpetuates only in infected leaves, not on grain. □